

COMPUTER SIMULATION OF MECHANICAL ALLOYING IN A SHAKER BALL MILL

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ABSTRACT

Little information currently exists on designing highly efficient ball mills for producing mechanically alloyed material. This work is an attempt at understanding the mechanisms of alloying in order to design better equipment. The problem of efficiency of mechanical alloying is investigated numerically by simulating the dynamics of a shaker ball mill. An object-oriented library has been developed and used to create a simulation software for such a system.

A number of numerical experiments were made in order to find out how internal properties of the system, such as the number of collisions, total kinetic energy, and the rate of energy dissipation due to heating of the balls, depended on both the frequency and amplitude of vibrations and the density of ball packing in the cylinder. The model of an ideal gas was used to validate the software.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical alloying has been around since the late 1960's and the principles were explained and established by Benjamin [1] but little information currently exists with respect to the design and operation of grinding equipment for the production of this material [2]. Commercial ball mills of a number of different types have been constructed and used, but most design and operating information is obtained by trial and error. Many of the attritor designs are based on the original work by Szegvari [3]. Some pilot attritor equipment has been used to generate experimental operating information [4] which is a starting basis but is specific to that equipment. Other studies in terms of applying theoretical analysis techniques are currently evolving [5,6]. Models put forth for different processing equipment are based upon energy principles combined with kinematics [7-10]. However due to the simplicity needed to allow a solution to the models, they are and will always be quite limited in application. A better approach is the development of a flexible simulation computer program which is the basis of this work. A simulation program can with minimal difficulty model many different parameters. These parameters, including geometry, can be easily changed to study operating performance and allow design information for optimization of processing equipment. As the model develops its sophistication will evolve accordingly. The work presented here is the first step in the evolution of this approach.

SIMULATION MODEL

The motion of balls inside the shaker ball mill is simulated in a 3-D space. The simulation system comprises the objects representing the cylinder itself and balls moving inside the cylinder. The balls are moving along the parabolic trajectories in a gravitational field:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{v}_0 t + \frac{\mathbf{g}t^2}{2}, \quad \mathbf{v}(t) = \mathbf{v}_0 + \mathbf{g}t, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = (u_x, u_y, u_z)^T$ is the position vector, $\mathbf{v} = (v_x, v_y, v_z)^T$ is the velocity vector and $\mathbf{g} = (0, 0, g)^T$ is the gravitation vector.

The motion of the cylinder is described as being harmonic in a vertical direction with the amplitude A and frequency f . For simplicity of calculations, it is assumed that the cylinder moves with constant acceleration during each half-period of oscillations, i.e. along a parabolic trajectory which corresponds to the second order spline approximation:

$$z(t) = v_0 t + \frac{at^2}{2}, \quad (2)$$

where for the first half-period ($0 \leq t < T/2$, $T = 1/f$ is the period of vibrations) $a = -32Af^2$, $v = 8Af$, and for the second half-period ($T/2 \leq t < T$) $a = 32Af^2$, $v = -8Af$. The assumption that the periodicity of the cylinder is of a parabolic form allows to calculate collision times directly by solving only second-order algebraic equations, while in the case of a sinusoidal form, the numerical solution is required.

The collisions between the balls and between the balls and the cylinder are assumed to be central, i.e. the tangential velocity of colliding balls is conserved. The cylinder is assumed to have an infinite mass, i.e. its velocity is not affected by the collisions. The collisions are presumed to be instant and one-to-one only, i.e. collisions between three or more objects are not allowed. We also presuppose that all energy lost during the collisions is transformed into heat.

Due to collisions, the normal velocity of colliding balls changes according to the law $|v_1 - v_2| = \epsilon |v_{10} - v_{20}|$, where v_1 and v_2 are the normal velocities of balls after the collision, v_{10} and v_{20} are the normal velocities of balls before the collision, and ϵ is the coefficient of restitution. From the laws of conservation of energy and impulse, the following formula can be obtained

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha - \epsilon & 1 + \epsilon - \alpha \\ \alpha & 1 - \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{10} \\ v_{20} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = \frac{(1 + \epsilon)m_1}{m_1 + m_2}$, m_1 and m_2 are masses of two colliding balls.

When a ball collides with the side wall of the cylinder, its normal velocity changes according to the relationship $v = -\epsilon v_0$. For the collision between a ball and the lid of the cylinder (which is moving), the normal velocity of the ball changes according to the relationship $v = v_c + \epsilon(v_c - v_0)$, where v_c is the velocity of the cylinder lid at the time of collision.

The assumption of instantaneous-type collisions is justified because the duration of a collision is short compared with the time scales of other events: times between collisions and the overall

simulation time. The above results are based on the theory of collision dynamics (see, for example, Johnson [11]). The Hertz theory [12] is used to estimate parameters of collision, such as collision duration and the volume of deformed area.

All collisions are assumed to be one-to-one. In the case when more than two objects collide simultaneously, the collision is handled consequently in pairs. For example, if balls A, B and C collide simultaneously, then the collision between A and B is handled first, independently of C, then the new velocities of A and B are calculated, and the collision between C and either A or B or both A and B is handled in the same manner. Such collision resolution scheme provides reasonably accurate results and significantly improves the efficiency of computations. The statistics of the simulations shows that the cases of simultaneous collisions between three or more objects are very rare. A one-to-one assumption of collisions is in accordance with the assumption of instantaneous-type collisions. Since, if the collision is assumed to be instant, the probability of a simultaneous collision of more than two objects is zero. But even if the duration of collision is taken into account, this probability is still very small.

Our main purpose was to investigate the energy-transfer properties of the system, i.e. how efficient the external energy of shaker vibrations is transformed into the internal energy of balls inside the shaker. With each collision the lost energy is transformed into heat. For a ball-to-ball collision this energy is

$$H_1 = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{m_1 m_2} \frac{v_n^2}{2} (1 - \epsilon^2) \quad (4)$$

and for a ball-to-cylinder collision, correspondingly,

$$H_2 = \frac{m_1 v_n^2}{2} (1 - \epsilon^2) \quad (5)$$

where v_n is the relative normal velocity of approach.

When a ball collides with the moving lid of the cylinder, the energy is contributed into the system of moving balls. One part of this energy is spent on heating the ball (H_2) and another one on changing the kinetic energy of the ball. The energy contributed to the system as a result of a ball-to-cylinder collision is

$$C = 2m_1 v_c (v_c - v_z) \quad (6)$$

where v_c is the velocity of the cylinder lid at the time of collision, and v_z is the vertical component of the ball velocity before the impact. As we can see, the energy contribution can be negative in the case when the lid and the ball move in the same direction while the ball moves faster than the lid.

Although the energy parameters are the main objectives of this study, it was also attempted to estimate the temperatures at the points of impact. The Hertz theory [2] was used to calculate the deformed volume during the impact and it was assumed that energy dissipated during the impact went into the heating of this deformed volume. Then the temperature rise was found based on the heat capacity of the material. The resulting formula for a ball-to-ball collision is

$$\Delta T = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{2}{5\delta\rho\pi^2} \right)^{0.8} \frac{1 - \epsilon^2}{c} \left(\frac{(r_1 + r_2)^3}{r_1^3 + r_2^3} \right)^{0.2} v_n^{0.4} \quad (7)$$

and for a ball-to-cylinder collision, correspondingly,

$$\Delta T = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{2}{5\delta\rho\pi^2} \right)^{0.8} \frac{1-\epsilon^2}{c} v_n^{0.4} \quad (8)$$

where $\delta = \frac{1-\mu^2}{E\pi}$, μ is the Poisson's ratio of material, E is the modulus of elasticity, ρ is the density of the ball material, c is the heat capacity of material, and r_1 and r_2 are the radii of balls.

IMPLEMENTATION

An object-oriented library developed to simulate the dynamics of granular-type materials [13] was used to simulate the shaker ball mill. The above library allowed to create a needed application very quickly by defining only application-specific properties of objects, such as laws of motion and collision rules. The object-oriented approach also allowed flexibility in changing and updating the simulation system. For example, if the shape of the shaker should be changed or some new kinds of lids were introduced, let say, spherical lids for a cylinder, all would be needed to do is to create a new class *SphericalLid* from the existing prototype class *Boundary* and define the specific properties of the new class, such as methods for determination of collision times with balls, motion laws (if the lid moves), and collision laws (how a ball changes its velocity when the collision occurs). Then the new object is included into the simulation system without changing anything else. It just fits into the slot left for any *Boundary*-successor object.

Our simulation system consists of objects representing balls and the cylinder. The main algorithm is based on the discrete event simulation scheme. The types of events handled in the simulation include events representing prediction of the trajectory of an object, collision events, as well as auxiliary events, such as output of statistical parameters at a specified moment of time to the file of results.

The simulation starts with assigning the balls random positions and velocities inside the cylinder and scheduling the "predict trajectory" events for each ball, as well as the "stop simulation" event at a desired time.

The handling of a "predict trajectory" event includes setting internal parameters of a ball ($\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{v}_0$) and scheduling the next "predict trajectory" event. Also all possible collision events for a ball are calculated and scheduled.

The handling of a "collision" event includes the following operations: all events scheduled for the currently colliding bodies are cancelled, the new parameters of collided bodies are calculated, and the "predict trajectory" events are scheduled at the present time for both colliding bodies.

With the increase of the number of balls the collision detection becomes a very time-consuming operation if each pair of balls is to be checked for a collision. To optimize the solution of this problem, a special data structure - rectangular map, is introduced. The whole simulation space is divided into a set of cells. Each ball "knows" in which cell it is currently moving, and collisions are detected only with balls in the neighboring cells of the map. When a ball moves from one cell to another, only the balls in the new neighboring cells must be checked for collisions.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

A number of numerical experiments had been made, in which the effect of the external parameters of the shaker, such as the frequency and amplitude of vibrations, on the internal parameters, such as rate of energy dissipation due to heating of the balls, number of collisions, kinetic energy of the balls, rate of energy flow into the system, and temperatures of impact, was investigated. One of the interesting results was that the dissipation of energy inside the system H is proportional to the amplitude of shaker vibrations A and to the third degree of frequency f , $H \sim Af^3$ (see Fig. 1 and 2, the following data was used in experiments: 10 steel balls, each of radius 10 mm; cylinder: height 103 mm, radius 31.5 mm).

Figure 1. Energy dissipation vs. Amplitude (frequency = 52.6 Hz)

Figure 2. Energy dissipation vs. Frequency of vibrations (amplitude = 10.9 mm)

The finding that internal milling energy is proportional to the third power of operating frequency is in keeping with the results of Streletskii [8], however the linear behavior of energy with amplitude is not. The effect of the density of ball packing and the shape of the shaker cylinder on the efficiency of shaker is currently being investigated.

VALIDATION

A model of an ideal gas was constructed to validate the simulation software. The ideal gas was simulated by a system of perfectly elastic small balls representing molecules of ideal gas moving inside the motionless cylinder. All collisions were supposed to be elastic, i.e. there was no energy loss in the system. Initially all balls were assigned equal velocities in random directions. The relationship between the kinetic energy of the balls (which remains constant), pressure on the walls of the cylinder, and the volume of the cylinder was investigated. Numerical experiments have shown that the $PV = RT$ gas law is satisfied. Here P is the pressure of the gas, V is the volume of the cylinder, T is the temperature of the gas (which is assumed to be proportional to the internal energy of the gas, i.e. kinetic energy of balls), and R is a constant. This result is of a particular interest, because this relationship does not depend on the shape of the cylinder, i.e. the ratio between the height and the radius.

Another validating result is that the distribution of velocities of molecules, which are all assigned equal values at the beginning of the simulation, soon comes to the Maxwell distribution of velocities (see Fig. 3). The initial magnitude of velocities in this experiment was set to 1000 mm/sec for all balls.

Figure 3. Distribution of velocities in an ideal gas model

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A software tool was developed to design more efficient shaker ball mills. The physical experimentation would be practically impossible, while the computer simulation allows to investigate behavior of internal energy parameters, velocities of balls and temperatures of impact.

This work has shown the usefulness and flexibility of the object-oriented approach in developing a simulation software for a specific problem. The object-oriented structure of the program allows changing the properties of simulated objects and adding new components into the system in a very natural way by inheriting new classes from existing prototypes and "plugging" them into the simulation scheme. The principles of the object-oriented design employed in the developing of the object-oriented library allowed to build a new application by creating application-specific "construction blocks" and inserting them into appropriate "slots" in the simulation engine. All what is left is to run the engine.

Work is in progress to investigate the efficiency of the shaker ball mills of different shapes and configurations. Also, a more precise simulation of collisions between the balls and the balls and boundaries, will be considered. It will include a consideration of the tangential friction forces, as well as the dynamics of impact. This will allow to simulate the shaking process more precisely and investigate the temperature rise more accurately.

The simulation program will be further verified in the near future with experimental measurements taken on an existing shaker ball mill after which the model was originally configured.

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